

Thank you for your support!

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Dear all backers,

On behalf of the team, I am delighted to let you know that our QuickStarter project (Is the More Frequent Extreme Weather in Tri-Cities Related to the Recent Rapid City Expansion?) is funded this morning! It is a pleasant surprise, and it cannot be achieved without support from you, for sure. We are now expecting to start the work under this project later in FY22. We look forward to sharing the results with you some time next year!

Thanks again,
Jingyi Chen, Zhao Yang and Yun Qian

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